

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Journal of Building Engineering

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/job

Modelica-based model predictive control for a CO₂ heat pump system: Case study in Oslo[☆]

Ge Song^{a,*}, Konstantin Filonenko^b, Xiaoqiao Wen^c, Razgar Ebrahimi^b,
Natasa Nord^a

^a Energy and Process Technology, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Kolbjørn Hejes vei 1 B, Trondheim, 7491, Norway

^b Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, Technical University of Denmark, 2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

^c School of Energy, Power and Mechanical Engineering, North China Electric Power University, Beijing, 102206, China

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Heat pump system
Thermal tank
Model predictive control
Modelica
Functional mock-up interface
Building flexibility

ABSTRACT

The proliferation of renewable energy technologies challenges the stability of the energy supply, requiring more flexibility from the energy demand. Consequently, methods for controlling heat pumps have received increasing attention. This study presents a Modelica-based Model Predictive Control (MPC) approach designed to maintain the supply water temperature within the 55 °C–75 °C range, while minimizing energy use and electricity costs over a one-year period. A detailed and high-fidelity model of a school building in Oslo, Norway, was developed in Modelica and exported as a Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU) to enable seamless integration with MATLAB/Simulink for the real time simulation and control implementation. The results demonstrated that the MPC strategy achieved annual electricity savings of 8.0 MWh (3.2 %) and 11,479 NOK (6.7 %) compared to a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller, and 85.07 MWh (25.9 %) and 46,967 NOK (22.8 %) compared to a fixed rule-based baseline controller. These savings were primarily attributed to the ability of MPC to anticipate and respond to future electricity price variations. The findings underscored the effectiveness of MPC as a robust and energy-efficient solution for thermal energy management systems.

1. Introduction

The transition towards sustainable energy solutions has brought forth the need for innovative approaches in heating systems, particularly in buildings. This paper focused on enhancing the flexibility of a CO₂ heat pump system in school buildings, with a particular emphasis on economic benefits and overcoming existing barriers by analyzing the economic viability of electricity price-based control strategies for the CO₂ heat pumps in Oslo, Norway.

1.1. Motivation

Use of renewable energies has seen significant growth over the past decade. According to reports, 2023 experienced the fastest rate of renewable capacity additions in two decades, with an increase of nearly 50 %, reaching close to 510 GW [1]. By 2028, it is estimated

[☆] The currency rate between NOK and EUR can be found from <https://www.xe.com/>, in this study 1 EUR = 10 NOK.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ge.song@ntnu.no (G. Song).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2025.114501>

Received 12 July 2025; Received in revised form 10 October 2025; Accepted 27 October 2025

Available online 29 October 2025

2352-7102/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

that renewable energy sources will account for 42 % of global electricity generation, with wind and solar PV contributing 25 % of that total [1]. In Norway, which boasts one of the highest shares of electricity production from renewable sources, approximately 136.49 TWh of electricity is generated from hydropower in a typical year, representing about 88 % of the country total power generation. Additionally, wind and solar power generated 15,051 GWh, making up about 10 % of the Norwegian electricity generation, with a total capacity of 5372 MW at the start of 2023 [2].

The integration of a high share of renewable energy sources can result in unstable electricity generation, as wind and solar generation are highly dependent on weather conditions. To address this issue, flexible energy systems are frequently suggested as a solution [3]. Flexibility may have various definitions and exhibits different impacts depending on the context, and thus it is quantified in several ways. For instance, system flexibility can refer to the ability to shift energy use from high-price to low-price periods [4]. Additionally, a flexible system can help mitigate both peak grid loads and peak electricity demands [5]. Further, flexibility means the ability to adjust its operation strategies to meet a given objective [6]. In a general way, a system with flexibility allows significant load control [7].

As an efficient electro-thermal device, utilizing heat pump in energy system is a promising way to increase system flexibility [8]. The dynamic operation of heat pumps enables thermal management and offers a degree of flexibility [9]. Heat pump systems allow the decoupling of energy supply from energy demand, as they can be paired with thermal energy storage [10]. Several studies have investigated the role of heat pumps in energy systems, particularly in heating systems. For instance, heating systems with heat pumps and thermal storage have been shown to achieve greater profitability in the German intraday market [11]. Additionally, households utilizing heat pumps can reduce costs by taking advantage of local energy markets through the inherent flexibility of heat pump systems [12].

However, incorporating larger storage into the system may result in delayed response times when adjusting the heating system, which challenges the ability to fully exploit the flexibility of heat pumps at the control level. To address this, MPC has been widely recognized as an effective solution [13]. Both short-term and long-term experiments have been conducted to compare the impact of MPC on heat pump and storage systems against standard heat pump controllers [14,15]. The findings indicate that MPC improves the coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump and reduces overall costs in both scenarios. Additionally, MPC has shown significant potential in domestic hot water (DHW) systems, where energy use decreases, and COP increases, while maintaining user comfort, regardless of prediction accuracy [16]. These studies highlight that MPC can effectively shift loads, reduce costs, and enhance efficiency in systems with heat pumps and energy storage.

1.2. State-of-the-art

Flexibility is crucial for the effective operation of energy systems, particularly when faced with challenges such as fluctuating weather conditions and electricity prices. Several studies have focused on how to evaluate and achieve flexibility in energy systems, revealing that heat pumps and energy storage often play a central role in enhancing the system flexibility. Walden et al. explored the flexibility of heat pumps, finding that the economic benefits increase as the operational load range of the heat pump expands [17]. However, they also identified a flexibility threshold, beyond which additional load flexibility provides diminishing returns. In one case study, a heat pump with a minimum load of 55 % exhibited a 19.3 % increase in net value compared to a heat pump without flexibility. Additionally, flexibility in energy systems can be analyzed in terms of time, power, and energy, rather than relying on a single indicator. The flexibility of a domestic energy system using a heat pump and thermal storage was analyzed under different energy supply scenarios in Ref. [18]. The system was simulated in three cases with varying wind energy shares of 7 %, 25 %, and 60 %, along with real-time electricity prices. The operation cost was optimized by adjusting the heat pump power and storage capacity, and the flexibility potential was quantified. The results indicated that 33 %–100 % of electric loads could be shifted to different times, with both flexibility potential and operational costs being highly sensitive to system design [18]. A thermal energy supply system incorporating a high-temperature heat pump and thermal energy storage was developed to respond to the variability in renewable energy generation and electricity prices in Ref. [19]. The system demonstrated flexible heat pump operation, using thermal storage to buffer the fluctuations in renewable energy and electricity costs. After the optimization to minimize the operational costs or emissions, the system achieved a 6 % cost reduction compared to a rule-based control strategy. Li et al. focused on optimizing the size and operation of an energy system comprising a heat pump, thermal energy storage, and photovoltaic (PV) panels to achieve energy and cost savings in Ref. [20]. Their findings showed that self-consumption and annual costs were reduced by 2.39 % and 6.61 %, respectively. Similarly, Gaucher-Loksts et al. compared three configurations based on Building Integrated Photovoltaic and an air source heat pump for powering a household, aiming to maximize energy savings in Ref. [21].

MPC has emerged as a powerful method for managing the complexity of building energy systems, which must handle thermal inertia and rapid environmental fluctuations. Its ability to forecast and optimize system behavior makes it well-suited for improving both energy efficiency and operational flexibility. Several studies have demonstrated the advantages of MPC over the rule-based or traditional control. For instance, MPC for a seasonal storage reduced annual heat losses to just 4 %, while supplying 80 % of heating demand in a district heating network [22]. Implementation of MPC in a multi-heat pump HVAC system achieved up to 37.3 % energy savings and significantly reduced occupant discomfort [23]. MPC has also proven superior in reducing peak loads and improving control stability when compared with feedback and fuzzy control methods [24]. Advanced frameworks, such as those in Refs. [25–27], further demonstrate MPC potential by integrating economic optimization, adaptive scheduling, and robust forecasting to enhance energy system performance. Collectively, these studies confirm that MPC is a key enabler for smarter and efficient energy management.

Although numerous studies have explored the application of MPC in building energy systems, its practical implementation —

particularly with real-time interaction — remains in the early stages. One of the most significant challenges is developing user-friendly, control-oriented, accurate, and computationally efficient building model [28]. To address this, open-source Modelica libraries such as Buildings [29] and IDEAS [30] offer valuable templates for model development. Some previous studies have used Modelica for real-time or control-oriented purposes [31,32], while others have applied MPC within real-time environments [33,34]. However, these works typically rely on simplified models and lack the integration of physically detailed, high-fidelity systems. For instance, MPC with Modelica was implemented in Ref. [35], but it was limited to basic thermal models, excluding hydraulics and thermodynamic cycles. In contrast, the current study represents a significant advancement by integrating MPC with a high-fidelity Modelica model that runs in real-time. This includes comprehensive modeling of hydraulic networks and thermodynamic behavior, enabling more realistic system responses and control decisions. The resulting framework bridges the gap between simulation and control, offering a novel and practical approach to real-time building energy optimization.

1.3. Research contributions

Integrating MPC with high-fidelity Modelica-based system models in real-time applications presents significant challenges, particularly in complex heating systems. Previous research has explored the use of Modelica for real-time simulation and control-oriented modeling, as well as the implementation of MPC within real-time simulation environments. However, the coupling of detailed, high-fidelity thermodynamic model with MPC frameworks remains limited. For instance, existing studies often apply MPC to simplified thermal models without incorporating intricate hydraulic or thermodynamic processes. This gap suggests that the seamless integration of detailed, high-fidelity system models with MPC remains relatively underexplored.

In response to this gap, recent studies have started to employ Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU)s as an interface for co-simulation between high-fidelity Modelica models and external MPC frameworks. For example, Erfani et al. developed an FMU-based co-simulation where a residential building model was coupled with MATLAB/Simulink MPC [36]. While these contributions illustrate the potential of FMU-based MPC integration, applications have largely focused on residential comfort-driven scenarios. By contrast, the present study extends this line of work by targeting system-level actuation and incorporating detailed thermodynamic processes in a CO₂ heat pump with thermal storage.

In this study, the use of the FMU technology enabling seamless interaction between a comprehensive Modelica-based system model and MATLAB/Simulink allowed this real-time data exchange and dynamic control updates. To the best of current knowledge, few studies have reported comparable implementations for complex heating systems, highlighting the novelty and practical relevance of the proposed framework. Specifically, the aim of this work was to optimize the operation of a school building energy system in Oslo, Norway, comprising a CO₂ heat pump and a thermal storage tank, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical control strategies and practical system deployment.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 details the methodology, including model development and control implementation. Section 3 presents the case study setup and simulation results. Section 4 discusses the findings and their implications. Section 5 concludes the study with key insights and recommendations for the future work.

2. Methodology

The study is based on the Norwegian demo case at Voldsløkka School and Cultural area, located in the mid/northern part of Oslo, shown in Fig. 1. This demo includes a newly constructed secondary school building (S-building) and the retrofitting of an existing cement factory (the Heidenreich building, H-building) to accommodate 810 pupils. The S-building and H-building are connected via a bridge on the second floor. The demo also features a cultural center, a cultural hall, and a sports hall. The school and cultural activities cover an area of 11,100 m² in the new construction and 2900 m² in the H-building. The school utilizes an innovative heating system that combines geothermal energy and a CO₂ heat pump to supply space heating. The CO₂ heat pump was designed to cover approximately 80–90 % of the space heating demand of the S-building, with district heating serving for peak loads, warming up

Fig. 1. Voldsløkka school.

domestic hot water, and as a backup. The CO₂ heat pump extracts heat from the boreholes and upgrades it for use in the building from two gas coolers, high temperature gas cooler and low temperature gas cooler. A 400L water tank serves as a buffer to store heat produced by the high temperature gas cooler. The system delivers hot water at three distinct temperature levels: 55 °C supply and 45 °C return for the radiator heating, 35 °C supply and 30 °C return for the floor heating (both from the high temperature gas cooler), and 28 °C supply and 24.1 °C return in summer, 14 °C supply and 18.8 °C return in winter for ventilation heating and cooling (from the low temperature gas cooler). Domestic hot water is delivered on demand via a separate line connected to the water storage tank. Valves and sensors are integrated throughout the system to enable desired temperature control. The schematic of the heating and cooling configuration is illustrated in Fig. 2. In this study, the supply temperature of the high temperature gas cooler of the heat pump and the tank temperature were selected as control variables in the MPC design.

The methodology of this study involved the integration of an MPC system with a Dymola-based simulation environment to optimize the operation of the CO₂ heat pump system in the observed building. As shown in Fig. 3, the MPC controller consists of a grey-box heat pump model and an optimization algorithm. The electricity price forecast was used as an economic signal for the objective function, while the tank temperature was introduced as a system constraint. These inputs were processed by the grey-box model and the optimization algorithm to compute the optimal compressor power. This control signal was then sent to a white-box heat pump model in the Dymola environment, which simulated the detailed thermodynamic behavior of the system. The white-box model interacted with a building model to reflect the overall thermal response of the building. In the co-simulation setup, the MPC (implemented in MATLAB/Simulink) exchanges inputs and outputs with the Modelica-based plant through the FMU interface at each control step, enabling real-time optimization under realistic system dynamics driven by varying electricity prices and thermal constraints. It is important to note that the RC building model representation was applied only within the model developed in Modelica. The predictive grey-box model used for MPC focuses on the CO₂ heat pump and water storage subsystem. This model was formulated at the system level, describing the energy balance and temperature evolution of the tank and the heat pump operation, while the building's thermal dynamics were captured through the FMU interface.

2.1. Detailed simulation model

The thermal energy system for the Voldsløkka School and Cultural area was designed with the ground source CO₂ heat pump as the

Fig. 2. Diagram of the components that were assessed in this study.

Fig. 3. MPC applied to heat pump control in buildings.

core of the heating and cooling system. Boreholes serve as the primary source of energy, providing free cooling and storing excess heat, while district heating is used to cover peak heating loads when required. Fig. 4 a illustrates the detailed Modelica model of the school heating system, capturing each subsystem and their interconnections. The system includes the five main components.

1. District Heating Model: This supplies supplemental heat during heat peak demand periods.
2. Building Model: Represents the thermal characteristics of the building and the heating and cooling demands.
3. Thermal Tank Model: Used for thermal energy storage, allowing the system to balance heating loads efficiently.
4. CO₂ Heat Pump Model: The core of the system that meets both heating and cooling demands by extracting energy from the boreholes.
5. Borehole Model: A model of the ground wells used to extract heat for the heat pump and store excess heat.

The detailed Modelica model of the observed system is shown in Fig. 4 a, where district heating and boreholes are connected to the CO₂ heat pump and thermal tank, which then distribute the heating and cooling throughout the building. The interaction between components follows the system layout, with heat and cooling being transferred based on real-time demand and energy availability.

Fig. 4 b shows the simplified system model, highlighting only the key components that were used in the MPC framework. These included the thermal tank, the CO₂ heat pump, and the building. The boreholes and district heating were not included in the simplified version used for control purposes, streamlining the system for MPC optimization. This simplified structure allowed efficient control of the heat pump without overcomplicating the MPC algorithm, focusing on the most critical elements of the system using electricity. Since the electricity price was used as the objective function for the optimization, only this core elements contributing to thus were used for the MPC development.

The CO₂ heat pump system features a single evaporator and two gas coolers, each supplying different temperature levels for heating and cooling. The evaporator operates with inlet temperatures of 3 °C in winter and 17 °C in summer, and outlet temperatures of 0 °C

Fig. 4. Modelica Simulation and Simplified MPC Structure of the CO₂ Heat Pump System. a. Detailed Modelica simulation of the thermal energy system. b. Simplified structure used for MPC.

and 12 °C, respectively. The high-temperature gas cooler supplies water at 55 °C and returns it at 30 °C, connected to radiators and the floor heating system, ensuring efficient heat distribution for space heating. The low-temperature gas cooler supplies water at 28 °C and returns it at 23 °C, integrated into the ventilation system for lower temperature heating and cooling needs.

The Modelica IDEAS library was utilized to simulate the system. The main component of the heat pump was modeled using the IDEAS.Fluid.HeatPumps.Carnot_y module from the IDEAS library. To model the two gas coolers as shown in Fig. 2, two heat exchanger components from the standard Modelica library were connected to the heat pump model to simulate the high temperature gas cooler and the low temperature gas cooler. By integrating these components, the model effectively captures the performance and efficiency of the CO₂ heat pump system under various operational conditions. The parameters of the heat pump model are shown in Table 1.

After constructing the model, the validation was carried out by inputting the actual measured inlet temperatures of the evaporator and the two gas coolers over a period of seven days. The comparison between the actual measured outlet temperature of the high-temperature gas cooler and the simulated value is shown in Fig. 5. The blue line represents the Modelica simulation results and the orange line represents the actual measured values. The close agreement between these results demonstrated the accuracy of the model, thereby completing the model validation. The validation was quantified according to ASHRAE Guideline 14–2014, with the coefficient of variation of the root mean square error (CV-RMSE) of 3.3 %, normalized mean bias error (NMBE) of 0.009 %, and an R² value of 96 %. All the model calibration parameters were within the recommended range and thereby the CO₂ heat pump model was estimated reliable for further use [37].

The building model was developed using the five key modules: the building envelope, internal heat gain, space heating system, ventilation system, and weather conditions. The building envelope module was developed using the TwoElements component from the IDEAS library [38], utilizing an RC thermal network to simulate heat transfer processes. The detailed parameters of the Thermal-ZoneTwoElements component are provided in Table A1 in Appendix. A constant internal heat gain of 130 kW (11.8 W/m² for the 11,000 m² floor area) was applied based on the national standard for energy demand calculation in buildings, Ns3031 [39] to represent the heat generated by equipment, lighting, and building occupants. The internal gain item in the model was calculated by summing all the three internal gains and considering the coincidence of these loads. To enhance computational efficiency for MPC purposes, the model focused solely on the high-temperature gas cooler from the CO₂ heat pump, which was responsible for space heating. The ventilation system was modeled as a mechanical air supply delivering 25 kg/s to maintain basic indoor air quality requirements, and domestic hot water was excluded as it was supplied by the district heating system. The building model in Modelica is shown in Fig. 6 a, and the validation against the measured data for the return water temperature from the building space heating system is depicted in Fig. 6 b. The Modelica model was initialized with a return water temperature of 20 °C, resulting in a short transient period at the beginning of the simulation. Validation metrics were calculated over the 60-day dataset, after the system reached steady operation. The resulting calibration parameters for the return water temperature were obtained as the following: CV-RMSE of 8.53 %, NMBE of -0.12 %, and R² of 87.54 %. Since all the model calibration parameters were within the recommended range, the building model was estimated reliable for further use [37].

2.2. Functional Mock-up interface for integrating modelica with MATLAB/simulink

To enable the integration of the Modelica model with MATLAB/Simulink for the MPC implementation, the FMU were utilized. An FMU is a package model that follows FMI standard, allowing dynamic models developed in Modelica or other simulation tools to be exported and used in various simulation environments such as MATLAB/Simulink. The process of using this method involves exporting the Modelica model as an FMU file using the Modelica modeling environment, which encapsulates the model equations, parameters, and solver settings. This FMU is then imported into MATLAB/Simulink using the FMI Toolbox allowing it to function as a Simulink block that interacts with MATLAB scripts, control logic, and other system components. In this study, the Modelica model of the heating system, which included the CO₂ heat pump, building model, and thermal tank, was converted into an FMU file as shown in Fig. 7 a. The FMU computed the heating demand for the space heating, \dot{Q}_{demand} , the outlet water temperature of the CO₂ heat pump high temperature gas cooler T_{hp} , and the water storage tank temperature T_{tank} at the previous time step $t - 1$. The MPC model, implemented in MATLAB, received these FMU outputs as inputs, optimizing system operation based on electricity price signals and past system states. The MPC model calculated the required heat pump compressor power, \dot{P} , for the current time step, t , which was fed back into the FMU to update the heating load for the next time step. This iterative process ensured real-time coordination between the real-time simulation and MPC for the optimal control. One of the key benefits of this approach is the ability to use the advanced optimization capabilities of MATLAB for the MPC algorithm while still leveraging the detailed physics-based modeling of the heating system in Modelica. The FMU allowed the system to run in a co-simulation environment where the control actions from the MPC were executed on the Modelica model in real time. This combined framework enhanced flexibility and accuracy while supporting a modular approach to system development. To validate the effectiveness of the FMU approach, the simulation results from the FMU were compared to the

Table 1
Parameters of the heat pump model.

Parameters	Value
Maximum Heating Capacity	152.3 kW (Winter)
Rated COP – Heating (Winter)	4.27
Max Discharge Pressure	100–110 bar
Compressor Modulation	10 %–100 %

Fig. 5. Heat Pump Model Structure and Validation of time series High-Temperature Gas Cooler return temperature a. Heat pump model developed in Modelica. b. Validation of simulated time series compared to measured data over time.

original results from the Modelica model. The validation process ensured that the exported FMU preserved the dynamic behavior and thermal response of the system. The comparison of the results showed strong alignment, confirming that the FMU-based model accurately replicated the performance of the original Modelica model. This validation step was essential to ensure that no significant deviations occur during the translation process. The validation results for the supply and return temperature, $T_{B,in}$ and $T_{B,out}$, to the space heating of the building model are presented in Fig. 7 b, where the outputs of the FMU and the Modelica model are plotted. The close agreement between the two sets of results demonstrates the reliability of the FMU-based approach for use in integrated MPC simulations.

Fig. 6. Building Model Structure and Validation: a. Building model developed in Modelica. b. Validation of simulated the return water temperature from the building model compared to measured data over time.

Fig. 7. Integration of Modelica-Based FMU with MPC for Real-Time Control: a. FMU Co-Simulation Framework. b. Validation of FMU Model Against Modelica Results for Supply and Return Temperatures in Space Heating.

2.3. Model predictive control

In this study, an MPC strategy was developed to optimize the operation of a hydronic heating system incorporating the CO₂ heat pump. The objective of the MPC was to improve system efficiency, reduce operational costs and enhance the flexibility of the heating system. The development and implementation of the MPC involved several key steps, which are detailed below.

The methodology began with the creation of a simulation model for the entire heating system, which included the CO₂ heat pump, water storage tank, and associated heating system components. The model was built using the IDEAS library in Modelica. The CO₂ heat pump model captures dynamic behaviors such as variations in mass flow rates and temperature differentials throughout the cycle. Additionally, a simplified CO₂ heat pump cycle model was established for the state space function of MPC. The mathematical representation of the CO₂ heat pump system was based on the following fundamental energy and mass balance equations. An hourly control and sampling interval was chosen to capture the main thermal dynamics while keeping the MPC computation manageable [40]:

Heat pump energy balance:

$$\dot{m}_{hp} \cdot c_p \frac{dT_{hp}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{flow} \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{hp} - T_{in}) + \dot{Q}_{in} \tag{1}$$

Water tank energy balance:

$$\dot{m}_{tank} \cdot c_p \frac{dT_{tank}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{flow} \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{hp} - T_{tank}) - \dot{Q}_{demand} \tag{2}$$

COP of the CO₂ heat pump:

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{in}}{\dot{P}} \quad (3)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity of the working fluid. \dot{m}_{hp} and \dot{m}_{tank} are the mass flow rate of the fluid, from the outlet of the gas cooler into the water tank and from the tank to the space heating system. T_{hp} , the heat pump temperature, is the outlet temperature of the heat pump gas cooler entering the water tank, and T_{tank} , the tank temperature, is the outlet temperature of the water tank supplying the space heating system. T_{in} represents the inlet temperature to the gas cooler. \dot{m}_{flow} is the mass flow rate of the fluid, both fluid out from the gas cooler to the tank and out from the tank to the space heating are the same, \dot{Q}_{in} denotes the thermal heat rate transferred from the heat pump to the water tank, while \dot{Q}_{demand} represents the thermal demand of the space heating system. The grey-box model used in the MPC represents the thermal behavior of the CO₂ heat pump and storage system. A constant COP value of 4.27 was used in this model, corresponding to the rated performance of the heat pump under standard winter conditions, as listed in Table 1. Dynamic variations in COP were not explicitly modeled, as the focus of this work was on demonstrating the FMU–MPC integration and system-level control framework.

For the MPC implementation, a reduced-order state-space model of the CO₂ heat pump and water storage tank was derived from the energy and mass balance Equations (1)–(3). The nonlinear equations were linearized around the nominal operating point corresponding to the rated heat pump capacity and the steady-state tank temperature. The resulting linearized model was expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{dT_{hp}}{dt} \\ \frac{dT_{tank}}{dt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_{hp} \\ T_{tank} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} \dot{Q}_{in} + \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{bmatrix} \dot{Q}_{demand} \quad (4)$$

The coefficients a_{ij} , b_i , e_i were obtained by taking partial derivatives of the nonlinear energy balance equations with respect to T_{hp} , T_{tank} , \dot{Q}_{in} , and \dot{Q}_{demand} at the nominal operating point.

The continuous-time model was then discretized using an 1-h sampling interval to yield the discrete state-space form as the following:

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k + Ed_k \quad (5)$$

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} T_{hp} \\ T_{tank} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$u = \dot{Q}_{in} \quad (7)$$

$$d = \dot{Q}_{demand} \quad (8)$$

This reduced model served as the internal predictive model within the MPC, while the detailed Modelica model was used for closed-loop co-simulation and validation via the FMU interface.

A data-driven identification approach using input–output data from the Modelica model was not adopted, as the governing equations were already validated. The analytical derivation ensures full physical consistency and transparency between the predictive and simulation models, which is particularly important for the FMU-based MPC applications.

2.4. Cost-optimized predictive control approach

The objective of the MPC strategy for the CO₂ heat pump system was to minimize operational costs while maintaining system efficiency and the tank temperature. To achieve this, the control strategy considers the impact of time-varying electricity prices, tank temperature, and heating demand. The MPC controller predicts system behavior over a future horizon and computes optimal control actions to achieve cost-effective and energy-efficient operation. In this study, the electricity cost was calculated as the product of the time-varying electricity price and the electricity use of the heat pump compressor.

The objective function J , minimized over a prediction horizon N , was defined as:

$$J = \int_0^{T_p} (EP(t) \cdot \dot{P}(t) + \lambda(T_{set} - T_c(t))^2) dt \quad (9)$$

Subject to:

$$x(0) = A \quad (10)$$

$$x(t) - F(x(t), u(t)) = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{P}(t) \leq \dot{P}_p \quad (12)$$

$$u_{min} \leq u(t) \leq u_{max} \quad (13)$$

where T_p is the prediction horizon that is the total duration over which the optimization is performed. $EP(t)$ denotes the time-varying electricity price, $\dot{P}(t)$ is the compressor power from the CO₂ heat pump, \dot{P}_p is the maximum compressor power. $T_c(t)$ is the instantaneous tank temperature supplied to the space heating in °C. In practice, this continuous formulation was discretized with a 1-h sampling interval for the MPC implementation. λ is the weighting factor that balances the trade-off between minimizing electricity costs and maintaining the tank temperature in a certain range. The value of λ in this study was set to a small value of 0.01 to emphasize the economic objective and clearly evaluate the response to the controller to the time-varying electricity price. The tank temperature was ensured by the hard constraints in the MPC formulation rather than by the quadratic penalty term. Tests with larger λ values reduced the price-responsiveness of the controller without significant improvement in thermal stability, thus the final choice ensured a balanced and interpretable formulation.

Weather conditions were modeled as disturbances to the system and treated as measured inputs. These inputs influence the heating demand, which was computed using the Modelica model. The resulting heating demand, in turn, affects the dynamics of both the heat pump and the water tank, and was incorporated into the MPC algorithm. The controller accounted for these measured disturbances when calculating the optimal control inputs for the next time step. The system state vector $x(t)$ was defined as $x(t) = [T_{hp}, T_{tank}]^T$, the control input $u(t)$ represents the compressor power from the heat pump \dot{P} , constrained by a lower limit u_{min} and an upper limit u_{max} .

2.5. Control experiment setting

To evaluate the performance of the MPC controller, two additional control strategies were implemented for comparative analysis. In total, three control scenarios were tested, as the following.

1. PI controller: The PI controller maintained the tank temperature at a constant setpoint of 60 °C. corresponding to the design supply temperature specified in the HVAC documentation. This temperature level was further referred to as the baseline supply and required that each controller maintain the outlet tank temperature as close as possible this level.
2. Baseline controller: The baseline controller operated according to a fixed compressor power schedule, applying the full power from 8:00 a.m. to 10:00 p.m., and reducing power to 80 % from 10:00 p.m. to 8:00 a.m.
3. MPC controller: The MPC controller aimed to balance electricity price fluctuations with the requirement to maintain the tank temperature within a specified range. It dynamically adjusted the compressor power based on the optimal control trajectory computed at each time step. Specifically, the MPC strategy increased compressor power during periods of low electricity prices to store thermal energy in the tank, and reduced power usage during periods of high prices to minimize energy costs while ensuring the tank temperature constraints were met.

Fig. 8. Influence of different \dot{m}_{flow} on tank temperature and control input using MPC

3. Results

In this section, the results of the study are presented to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed MPC-based control strategy for optimizing the operation of the heat pump and thermal tank system. The analysis begins with the tuning process for the MPC operating point and prediction horizon, highlighting the trade-offs between temperature control and cost efficiency. The performance of the MPC is then compared against a conventional PI controller, focusing on key metrics such as energy use, operational cost savings, and temperature control. Additionally, the flexibility realized through the MPC in response to varying electricity prices and heat demand is explored. These results provide a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed approach practicality and its advantages in managing complex energy systems.

3.1. Tuning of the MPC operating point and prediction horizon

The influence of varying \dot{m}_{flow} on the performance of the MPC control signal is shown in Fig. 8. The upper subplot shows tank temperature profiles for different flow rates, where all the scenarios maintain the desired temperature range, indicating the robustness of MPC in achieving the desired water temperature in the tank. The lower subplot illustrates the compressor power, with higher mass flow rates resulting in reduced compressor power requirements due to improved heat transfer efficiency. A higher flow rate improved the thermal exchange between the gas cooler and the water tank, reducing the required temperature lift across the heat pump cycle. As a result, the compressor consumed less electrical power to achieve the same heating effect. However, beyond 2 kg/s, the incremental improvement becomes marginal, indicating diminishing returns in terms of energy savings. Additionally, beyond the initial transient period, this operating point demonstrates the best ability to maintain temperatures above 55 °C, which represents the lower boundary of the tank temperature range.

The impact of different prediction horizons on the simulated signals in the MPC-controlled system are shown in Fig. 9, specifically focusing on the water tank temperature and the compressor power. The longer prediction horizons allowed the MPC to anticipate future electricity price variations earlier, enabling the controller to optimize the compressor power usage more effectively and minimize costs. However, prediction horizons of 30 h led to a noticeable decline in the tank temperature, as shown in the upper subplot, where the temperature frequently dropped below the required 55 °C threshold. This increased the risk of violating the operational requirements of the system. While price optimization was prioritized by the MPC, maintaining the temperature objectives was critical. The horizon of 24 h was chosen as it showed a balance between the price minimization and the temperature tracking terms, ensuring the supply temperature above 55 °C for most of the time while effectively responding to price variations. In addition, a step-response analysis of the CO₂ heat pump and storage tank system indicated a dominant time constant of approximately 4–5 h. The selected 24-h prediction horizon thus covers about five times the main dynamic time scale of the system, ensuring that the MPC captures the essential thermal dynamics while remaining computationally efficient.

Based on the results in Figs. 8 and 9, for this study, the \dot{m}_{flow} of 2 kg/s and the prediction horizons of 24 h were selected for use in this study, balancing energy efficiency, system stability, and control performance.

Fig. 9. Influence of different prediction horizons on tank temperature and control input using MPC

3.2. Comparison of annual performance for different control strategies

The performance comparison among the MPC controller, the baseline controller, and the PI controller for the CO₂ heat pump system is shown in Fig. 10. The results show a control example for January, which represents the coldest conditions during the year. The top subplot illustrates the tank temperature dynamics under the PI controller, the baseline controller, and MPC controller, along with the heat pump outlet temperature from the MPC results. This was included for reference, as mentioned above, since T_{hp} , T_{tank} were state variables in the MPC algorithm. The middle subplot compares the compressor power to the heat pump under MPC, PI, and the baseline control strategies. The bottom subplot provides insights into the external disturbances, including normalized heat demand for 2024 (the red line) and the hourly electricity price profile in Oslo (the black line). The pronounced electricity price peak around the 400th hour represents a short-term market imbalance captured in the Nord Pool dataset during a cold period. The normalized heat demand was calculated using the Modelica model and scaled to allow easier comparison with the electricity price.

Fig. 10. Comparison of PI, baseline and MPC Controller performance.

In Fig. 10, it can be seen that the PI controller (the pink line) maintains the tank temperature steadily at 60 °C, the compressor power was adjusted continuously to ensure that the tank temperature reached and stayed at this setpoint. However, the PI controller did not respond to electricity price variations. The compressor power trend largely followed the heat demand. When heat demand increased, the compressor power also increased. The baseline results (the green line) show that, since the compressor power follows a fixed schedule as introduced earlier, the tank temperature trend was opposite to the heat demand trend. When heat demand was high, meaning more heat was drawn from the tank, the fixed compressor power was insufficient, and the tank temperature dropped. When heat demand was low, the fixed compressor input caused the tank temperature to rise. Both the PI and the baseline controllers showed some level of dynamic thermal response, but neither considers electricity price in their operation. This was particularly evident during the significant price peak between the 400th and 450th hour. During this period, electricity prices spiked, while the heat demand also increased, peaking around the 420th hour. Consequently, the compressor power input from the PI controller remained high, similar to the baseline controller, which could result in high electricity costs. In contrast, the MPC controller considers both the tank temperature and electricity price. As shown in Fig. 10, the MPC controller reduced the compressor power input during the high-price period. The MPC algorithm thus made an optimal trade-off between maintaining the required tank temperature and minimizing electricity costs. While the baseline controllers control the tank temperature reactively, MPC anticipates future electricity price changes and adjusts the compressor power proactively, achieving a balance between cost minimization and temperature constraint satisfaction—illustrating its key functional advantage over conventional control strategies.

The same control strategies were applied over the course of an entire year, and the results are presented in Fig. 11. The trends observed are consistent with those from the January case. The PI controller continuously adjusted the compressor power to maintain the tank temperature at the setpoint of 60 °C. The baseline controller operated on a fixed compressor power schedule, as previously described. In contrast, the MPC controller dynamically balanced the trade-off between maintaining tank temperature within acceptable thresholds and minimizing electricity costs. When considering only the base cost of electricity (excluding grid tariffs and taxes), the total electricity bills for the MPC, PI, and the baseline controllers were 159,440 NOK, 170,919 NOK, and 206,407 NOK, respectively. This indicates that the MPC controller reduced electricity costs by 6.7 % compared to the PI controller and by 22.8 % compared to the baseline controller.

3.3. Performance comparison of MPC with baseline and PI control

The key performance differences among the MPC, PI and the baseline strategies are shown in Fig. 12. The blue bars represent annual electricity use, with the MPC achieving the lowest usage at approximately 243 MWh, followed by the PI controller at 251 MWh, and the baseline at 328 MWh. The orange bars show the electricity cost, where the MPC also resulted in the lowest cost (159.4 kNOK), compared to PI (170.9 kNOK), and the baseline (206.4 kNOK). Although the energy use for MPC was only about 3.2 % lower than that of PI, the cost saving are more significant at 6.7 %. In contrast, the PI controller achieved a 23.5 % reduction in energy use compared to the baseline, but only a 17.2 % cost reduction. These findings suggest that while MPC offers moderate energy saving over PI, its ability to respond to dynamic electricity prices provides a greater advantage in cost reduction. Compared to the baseline, the MPC demonstrated considerable savings in both energy and cost, with a slightly greater benefit observed in energy reduction due to its consideration of the tank temperature. Overall, control strategies that prioritize temperature tracking tend to improve energy efficiency, while those that respond to electricity prices are more effective in reducing costs. The MPC approach achieved a balance between these objectives, resulting in simultaneous energy and cost savings. A quantitative summary of the control performance metrics is referred to Table A2 in Appendix.

4. Discussion

The heating system of the case study school building represents a relatively complex heating system. Simplifying this system to build a model in Modelica for the study required careful consideration. Since the study primarily focused on the implementation of the MPC for the heat pump flexibility, special attention was given to ensuring the accuracy of the heat pump model and in this case the CO₂ heat pump. Typically, CO₂ heat pump models in Modelica are built using commercial libraries like TIL. However, considering computational resources and the practical applicability of the model, the standard heat pump model available in the open Modelica library IDEAS was chosen. This model was connected to two heat exchangers to simulate the two gas coolers as in the real system of the case study building, and its calibration was validated to ensure reliability.

Another challenging aspect of the study was tuning the MPC to the physical model in Modelica. After exploring various methods, translating the Modelica model to an FMU format and conducting co-simulation in MATLAB/Simulink was selected as the approach. This method not only addressed the integration challenges but also serves as a useful reference for future studies. For the MPC design, the state-space model of the heat pump and thermal tank was used, which represents a standard approach. Significant effort was required to tune the Modelica model and MPC algorithms together, including selecting appropriate parameters and constraints to ensure successful implementation.

The application of the MPC resulted in notable reductions in both electricity and operational costs, achieving saving of 8.0 MWh (3.2 %) and 11,479 NOK (6.7 %) compared to the PI controller and 85.07 MWh (25.9 %) and 46,969 NOK (22.8 %) compared to the baseline controller. These outcomes highlight the advantages of MPC in enhancing energy and economic performance by dynamically responding to electricity price fluctuations and system conditions. Further analysis of the specific operational scenarios contributing to these savings may offer deeper insights into the practical benefits and implementation strategies for MPC in similar systems. The implementation of the MPC also demonstrated its potential to enhance building flexibility. By actively managing the heating system in

Fig. 11. Comparison of Tank Temperature, Control Input, and Between PI, baseline and MPC Controllers over One Year.

Fig. 12. Annual electricity use and costs for MPC, baseline, and PI controllers.

response to electricity price signals and heat demand variations, MPC enabled the building to act as a flexible demand resource. This adaptability was critical for integrating renewable energy sources and addressing the increasing instability on the supply side.

The MPC controller occasionally allowed the tank temperature to fall below the minimum threshold during periods of exceptionally high electricity prices, which could risk insufficient heat supply to maintain indoor temperature setpoints. This issue could be mitigated by adjusting the mass flow rate from the gas cooler to the thermal tank to enhance heat transfer efficiency. In this case study, the mass flow rates from the gas cooler to the tank and from the tank to the space heating system were fixed at 2 kg/s to simplify the MPC algorithm. In the future work, the mass flow rate should be considered as an additional manipulated variable within the MPC framework. Furthermore, this study did not address the thermal flexibility of the building envelope. The dynamic response of the indoor temperature to the low supply temperatures was not included in the MPC formulation. Future research will aim to incorporate building envelope dynamics into the control strategy to enhance the overall effectiveness of the MPC implementation.

While the results are promising, implementing MPC in real-world systems entails addressing challenges such as computational demand, the need for highly accurate models, and ensuring robustness under unexpected disturbances. Future research could focus on mitigating these challenges, enhancing the long-term reliability of MPC-controlled systems, and exploring strategies for widespread adoption. The practical experience gained in this study, particularly regarding model simplification, FMU integration, and MPC tuning,

offers valuable guidance for similar applications in building energy systems.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated a modelica-based MPC framework for a CO₂ heat pump system with water tank in a school building in Oslo, demonstrating its feasibility and effectiveness through an FMU-based co-simulation platform. The key novelty lies in the integration of a high-fidelity Modelica model with MPC via the FMU interface, enabling real-time interaction between detailed thermodynamic and hydraulic dynamics and the predictive control algorithm.

The case study highlights the significant energy and cost reduction achieved of 8.0 MWh (3.2 %) and 11,479 NOK (6.7 %) compared to the PI controller and 85.07 MWh (25.9 %) and 46,967 NOK (22.8 %) compared to the baseline controller, while ensuring compliance with operational constraints such as maintaining the tank temperatures above 55 °C for most of the operation period. The MPC ability to leverage dynamic electricity prices and efficiently adapt to system disturbances underscored its superiority over traditional control methods like PI.

In addition to economic advantages, the MPC demonstrated enhanced flexibility by adapting to varying electricity prices and thermal demands. This adaptability illustrates its potential to meet the increasing demand for flexibility in the energy sector, where supply-side uncertainties are prevalent. The results emphasized the importance of predictive control in utilizing demand-side flexibility to address challenges such as fluctuating renewable energy production and peak load management.

While the findings are promising, the real-world implementation of MPC presents challenges such as computational demands, the need for highly accurate system modeling, and tuning the MPC to achieve optimal performance. Future work should focus on addressing these challenges by exploring the real-time optimization techniques, further calibration of system models, and extending the control approach to other building types or larger systems. Additionally, investigating the long-term reliability and maintenance of the MPC systems will be crucial for ensuring their widespread adoption in practical applications.

Overall, this research highlights the potential of MPC to transform heating system control by achieving substantial cost savings, improving system adaptability, and contributing to the flexibility of energy systems in buildings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ge Song: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Konstantin Filonenko:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology. **Xiaoqiao Wen:** Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Razgar Ebrahimi:** Supervision, Project administration. **Natasa Nord:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This publication has been jointly written within the cooperative projects “Key technologies and demonstration of combined cooling, heating and power generation for low-carbon neighbourhoods/buildings with clean energy – ChiNoZEN” and “Climate positive Circular Communities - ARV”. The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding support from the Research Council of Norway (ERC project number 304191 - ENERGIX) and from the Ministry of Science and Technology of China (MOST project number 2019YFE0104900) and European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036723 (ARV project).

Appendix

Table A1
Parameters of the ThermalZoneTwoElements Building Model

Parameter	Description	Value	Unit
V_{Air}	Air volume of the thermal zone	39,759	m ³
α_{Rad}	Coefficient of linearized radiation heat transfer between walls	5	W/(m ² ·K)
$n_{Orientations}$	Number of wall orientations	2	–
A_{Win}	Window area (by orientation)	(600, 600)	m ²
$A_{Transparent}$	Transparent area (solar radiation transmitted)	(600, 600)	m ²
α_{Win}	Indoor convective coefficient for windows	2.7	W/(m ² ·K)
R_{Win}	Thermal resistance of windows	1.66×10^{-4}	K/W

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Parameter	Description	Value	Unit
g_{Win}	Solar energy transmittance of windows	0.4	–
$ratio_{WinConRad}$	Ratio of convective to radiative heat emission for windows	0.09	–
A_{Ext}	Exterior wall area (by orientation)	(10,000, 2000)	m ²
α_{Ext}	Convective coefficient for exterior walls	8.7	W/(m ² ·K)
n_{Ext}	Number of RC elements (exterior walls)	1	–
R_{Ext}	Thermal resistance (wall, inside to outside)	1×10^{-3}	K/W
R_{ExtRem}	Remaining resistance between capacity and outer surface	0.1×10^{-6}	K/W
C_{Ext}	Heat capacity of exterior wall	3.8×10^7	J/K
A_{Int}	Interior wall area	16,965	m ²
α_{Int}	Convective coefficient for interior walls	8.8	W/(m ² ·K)
n_{Int}	Number of RC elements (interior walls)	1	–
R_{Int}	Thermal resistance of interior walls	9×10^{-8}	K/W
C_{Int}	Heat capacity of interior walls	1.7×10^7	J/K

Table A2

Quantitative comparison of control performance metrics among MPC, PI, and baseline strategies

Metric	MPC	PI	Baseline
Annual electricity use (MWh)	243	251	328
Electricity cost (kNOK)	159.4	170.9	206.4
Energy reduction vs. Baseline (%)	25.9 %	23.5 %	–
Cost reduction vs. Baseline (%)	22.8 %	17.2 %	–
Energy reduction vs. PI (%)	3.2 %	–	–
Cost reduction vs. PI (%)	6.7 %	–	–
Control simulation time (h)	~2.5	~1.8	~1.2
Peak tank temperature deviation (°C)	15	3	5
RMSE of tank temperature (°C)	4.5	2.2	3.8

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

References

- [1] IEA, *Renewables 2023*, IEA, Paris, 2024.
- [2] Norwegian Ministry of Energy, *Energy Facts Norway (2024)*, Available at: <https://www.energifaktanorge.no>.
- [3] G. Reynders, R. Amaral Lopes, A. Marszal-Pomianowska, D. Aelenei, J. Martins, D. Saelens, Energy flexible buildings: an evaluation of definitions and quantification methodologies applied to thermal storage, *Energy Build.* 166 (2018) 372–390.
- [4] J. Le Dréau, P. Heiselberg, Energy flexibility of residential buildings using short term heat storage in the thermal mass, *Energy* 111 (2016) 991–1002.
- [5] F. Oldewurtel, A. Ulbig, A. Parisio, G. Andersson, M. Morari, Reducing peak electricity demand in building climate control using real-time pricing and model predictive control, in: 49th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control, (CDC), 2010, pp. 1927–1932.
- [6] Z. Tian, X. Li, J. Niu, R. Zhou, F. Li, Enhancing operation flexibility of distributed energy systems: a flexible multi-objective optimization planning method considering long-term and temporary objectives, *Energy* 288 (2024) 129612.
- [7] A. Arteconi, D. Costola, P. Hoes, J.L.M. Hensen, Analysis of control strategies for thermally activated building systems under demand side management mechanisms, *Energy Build.* 80 (2014) 384–393.
- [8] S. Steinle, M. Zimmerlin, F. Mueller, L. Held, M.R. Suriyah, T. Leibfried, Time-dependent flexibility potential of heat pump systems for smart energy system operation, *Energies* 13 (2020) 4148.
- [9] N.J. Hewitt, Heat pumps and energy storage – the challenges of implementation, *Appl. Energy* 89 (1) (2012) 37–44.
- [10] M. Evens, A. Mugnini, A. Arteconi, Design energy flexibility characterisation of a heat pump and thermal energy storage in a comfort and climate box, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 216 (2022) 119154.
- [11] Z. Marijanovic, P. Theile, B.H. Czock, Value of short-term heating system flexibility – a case study for residential heat pumps on the German intraday market, *Energy* 249 (2022) 123664.
- [12] Z. You, S.D. Lumpp, M. Doepfert, P. Tzscheuschler, C. Goebel, Leveraging flexibility of residential heat pumps through local energy markets, *Appl. Energy* 355 (2024) 122269.
- [13] C. Baumann, P. Kepplinger, Application of a flexibility estimation method for domestic heat pumps with reduced system information and data, *Clean. Energy Syst.* 6 (2023) 100081.
- [14] S. Kuboth, F. Heberle, T. Weith, M. Welzl, A. König-Haagen, D. Brüggemann, Experimental short-term investigation of model predictive heat pump control in residential buildings, *Energy Build.* 204 (2019) 109444.
- [15] S. Kuboth, T. Weith, F. Heberle, M. Welzl, D. Brüggemann, Experimental long-term investigation of model predictive heat pump control in residential buildings with photovoltaic power generation, *Energies* 13 (2020) 3222.
- [16] C. Baumann, G. Huber, J. Alavanja, M. Preißinger, P. Kepplinger, Experimental validation of a state-of-the-art model predictive control approach for demand side management with a hot water heat pump, *Energy Build.* 285 (2023) 112923.
- [17] J.V.M. Walden, P. Stathopoulos, The impact of heat pump load flexibility on its process integration and economics, *J. Clean. Prod.* 462 (2024) 142643.
- [18] C. Schellenberg, L. Dimache, J. Lohan, Grid-edge technology - exploring the flexibility potential of a heat pump and thermal energy storage system, *E3S Web Conf.* 111 (2019).
- [19] J.V.M. Walden, M. Bähr, A. Glade, J. Gollasch, A.P. Tran, T. Lorenz, Nonlinear operational optimization of an industrial power-to-heat system with a high temperature heat pump, a thermal energy storage and wind energy, *Appl. Energy* 344 (2023) 121247.
- [20] B. Li, Z. Liu, Y. Zheng, H. Xie, L. Zhang, Economy and energy flexibility optimization of the photovoltaic heat pump system with thermal energy storage, *J. Energy Storage* 100 (2024) 113526.

- [21] E. Gaucher-Loksts, A. Athienitis, M. Ouf, Design and energy flexibility analysis for building integrated photovoltaics-heat pump combinations in a house, *Renew. Energy* 195 (2022) 872–884.
- [22] Z. Wei, P.W. Tien, J. Calautit, J. Darkwa, M. Worall, R. Boukhanouf, Investigation of a model predictive control (MPC) strategy for seasonal thermochemical energy storage systems in district heating networks, *Appl. Energy* 376 (2024) 124164.
- [23] B. Yue, B. Su, F. Xiao, A. Li, K. Li, S. Li, R. Yan, Q. Lian, A. Li, Y. Li, X. Fang, X. Liang, Energy-oriented control retrofit for existing HVAC system adopting data-driven MPC – methodology, implementation and field test, *Energy Build.* 295 (2023) 113286.
- [24] J. Zhao, J. Li, Y. Shan, Research on a forecasted load-and time delay-based model predictive control (MPC) district energy system model, *Energy Build.* 231 (2021) 110631.
- [25] S. Wang, L. Kong, C. Liu, G. Cai, MPC-based energy optimization and regulation for zero-carbon energy supply building, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 82 (2024) 1196–1210.
- [26] G. Fan, C. Peng, X. Wang, P. Wu, Y. Yang, H. Sun, Optimal scheduling of integrated energy system considering renewable energy uncertainties based on distributionally robust adaptive MPC, *Renew. Energy* 226 (2024) 120457.
- [27] C. Qian, N. He, Z. Cheng, R. Li, L. Yang, Double-layer optimal scheduling method for solar photovoltaic thermal system based on event-triggered MPC considering battery performance degradation, *Energy* 304 (2024) 132233.
- [28] J. Drgoña, J. Arroyo, I. Cupeiro Figueroa, D. Blum, K. Arendt, D. Kim, E.P. Ollé, J. Oravec, M. Wetter, D.L. Vrabie, L. Helsen, All you need to know about model predictive control for buildings, *Annu. Rev. Control* 50 (2020) 190–232.
- [29] M. Wetter, W. Zuo, T.S. Nouidui, X. Pang, Modelica buildings library, *J. Build. Perform. Simul.* 7 (4) (2014) 253–270.
- [30] R. Baetens, R. De Coninck, F. Jorissen, D. Picard, L. Helsen, D. Saelens, Openidea-an open framework for integrated district energy simulations, in: *Building Simulation*, 2015, pp. 345–354.
- [31] A. Kumar, A. Narasimhan, T. Rajendran, S. Velut, Digital Twin Applications Using a Cloud Native Modelica Platform, 2022.
- [32] F. Delussu, D. Manzione, R. Meo, G. Ottino, M. Asare, Experiments and comparison of digital twinning of photovoltaic panels by machine learning models and a cyber-physical model in modelica, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inf.* 18 (6) (2022) 4018–4028.
- [33] E. O’Dwyer, I. Pan, R. Charlesworth, S. Butler, N. Shah, Integration of an energy management tool and digital twin for coordination and control of multi-vector smart energy systems, *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 62 (2020) 102412.
- [34] C. Ates, D. Bicat, R. Yankov, J. Arweiler, R. Koch, H.-J. Bauer, Model predictive evolutionary temperature control via neural-network-based digital twins, *Algorithms* 16 (8) (2023) 387.
- [35] A. Clausen, K. Arendt, A. Johansen, F.C. Sangogboye, M.B. Kjærgaard, C.T. Veje, B.N. Jørgensen, A digital twin framework for improving energy efficiency and occupant comfort in public and commercial buildings, *Energy Inf.* 4 (2) (2021) 40.
- [36] A. Erfani, T. Jafarnejad, S. Roels, D. Saelens, In search of optimal building behavior models for model predictive control in the context of flexibility, *Build. Simulat.* 17 (1) (2024) 71–91.
- [37] A.G. Ashrae, Guideline 14-2014: Measurement of Energy, Demand, and Water Savings, American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air Conditioning Engineers, 2014. Atlanta, Georgia.
- [38] F. Jorissen, G. Reynders, R. Baetens, D. Picard, D. Saelens, L. Helsen, Implementation and verification of the IDEAS building energy simulation library, *J. Build. Perform. Simul.* 11 (6) (2018) 669–688.
- [39] N. Standards Norway, **Energy Performance of Buildings - Calculation of Energy and Power Demand.**
- [40] A. Erfani, T. Jafarnejad, S. Roels, D. Saelens, Impact of dataset sampling period on building thermal models used for flexibility activation, *Build. Environ.* 262 (2024) 111775.